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Infrared Spectral Studies of Solid Solutions of Lead Hydroxylapatite with Arsenate

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LEAD hydroxylapatite, (PbHA), $Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ is very important among the apatite series of compounds¹. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic substitution reactions¹. The isomorphous replacement of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ by $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ in PbHA results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of PbHA with arsenate according to the following equation

As a part of a series of physico-chemical investigations on the samples the present work deals with the infrared spectral studies of these samples.

Experimental

The details of preparation and characterisation of the samples were reported earlier². The samples used for infrared studies were acetone, washed and air dried. The i-r tracing was carried on Carl-Zeiss Jena UR 10 Double beam instrument in Nujol-mull medium.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of the samples by the method specially worked out³ were given in the Table 1. From the analytical data the molecular

TABLE 1. ANALYTICAL DATA OF LEAD HYDROXYLAPATITE AND ITS SOLID SOLUTIONS WITH ARSENATE

Sam- ple No.	Wt%			Molecular formulae	g.atom ratio Pb P+As
	Pb	P	As		
1.	77.45	6.95	—	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$	1.68
2.	76.26	5.82	2.49	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{5.1}(AsO_4)_{0.9}(OH)_2$	1.67
3.	75.04	4.61	5.14	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{4.1}(AsO_4)_{1.9}(OH)_2$	1.67
4.	73.75	3.31	8.01	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{3.0}(AsO_4)_{3.0}(OH)_2$	1.67
5.	72.85	2.40	10.02	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{2.2}(AsO_4)_{3.8}(OH)_2$	1.68
6.	71.52	0.11	13.56	$Pb_{10}(PO_4)_{1.0}(AsO_4)_{5.0}(OH)_2$	1.68
7.	70.46	—	15.31	$Pb_{10}(AsO_4)_6(OH)_2$	1.68

formula of each sample was calculated and the molar gram atomic ratios of $\frac{Pb}{As+P}$ of each of the sample was calculated and found to have the value ~ 1.68 (theoretical 1.67). The i-r runs of a representative set of the samples (Sl. No. 1, 3, 5, 7 of Table 1) were given in Fig. 1. The lead hydroxylapatite and

Fig. 1. Infrared Spectra of solid solution of Lead hydroxylapatites in the range between 400–1200 cm^{-1} (A, B, C, D spectra corresponds to the spectra of the samples No. 1, 3, 5, 7 of Table 1).

its solid solutions have hexagonal crystalline structure⁴ and are interesting examples of solid state of fairly simple molecules of tetrahedral symmetry where bands become allowed due to relaxation of the molecular symmetry selection rules due to the influence of site symmetry. The ideal symmetry of tribasic phosphate and/or arsenate ion in the free or undistorted state is tetrahedral—a member of T_d point group. In this ideal symmetry condition only a few absorption bands corresponding to ν_4 (570 cm^{-1}) and ν_3 (1075 cm^{-1}) of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ were clearly observed. From the spectra of the samples (Fig. 1) it could be seen that the ν_3 and ν_4 frequencies corresponding to phosphate ion are shifted to lower frequencies and the shape of the peaks was being effected by the introduction of $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ into the samples. From the consideration of the peak shifts and alteration of peak length ratios one can infer that the phosphate structure is effected by the introduction of $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ into the samples. The shift of the ν_3 and ν_4 of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ vibrations to lower frequencies may be due to the effect of binding energy and atomic mass. In Barnes expression⁵

$$V = \frac{1}{2\pi c} \sqrt{\frac{K}{\mu}}$$

which gives a relationship between frequency, atomic mass and force constant. The vibration frequency is dependent on the reduced mass μ of the participating atoms and the restoring forces K between atoms, all other terms remaining constant. When the equilibrium distance between the positive and negative atoms of the molecule is decreased, K generally increases in the above equation. This equilibrium distance depends on the ionic radii of the participating atoms in the molecule. The effect of diminished force constant is reinforced by the increase in mass of the substituted $(AsO_4)^{3-}$ ion which shifts ν_3 and ν_4 of $(PO_4)^{3-}$ bands to lower frequencies. This theoretical explanation agrees well with the experimental data.

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Chemistry of Benzoquinolines. Part VI

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IN our previous paper¹ we have reported the reactions of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I) with aromatic aldehydes. The mono styryl derivatives so formed were oxidised to mono-carboxylic acid, which on decarboxylation gave 4-methyl-7,8-benzoquinoline. In the present paper we have studied the reactions of 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline(I) further.

Fig. (I) R = CH₃
 (II) R = -CH = CHC₆H₅
 (III) R = *m*-O₂NC₆H₄CH = CH-
 (IV) R = COOH
 (V) R = H

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I) m.p. 54°-55° was prepared in accordance with Combes². 2,4-Distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline (II) m.p. 180°-81° was prepared by refluxing 2,4-dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (1 mole) with excess of benzaldehyde (4 moles) for 32 hr in presence of acetic anhydride. 2,4-Di-(3'-nitro) styryl-7,8-benzoquinoline m.p. 281°-82° was prepared by heating the base (I; 1 mole) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (2 moles) in presence of acetic anhydride at 160° for 4 hr. The above condensation did not take place when fused zinc chloride was used as condensing agent. The procedure followed by Singh and Lal³ also failed to give any fruitful result, though time of refluxing was increased to 96 hr.

The presence of -CH = CH- in distyryls (II) and (III) is confirmed by infrared absorption at 1600 cm⁻¹. latter shows strong bands at 1516 cm⁻¹ and 1341 cm⁻¹, both very strong characteristic for -NO₂ group.

The 2,4-distyryl-7,8-benzoquinoline was oxidised with KMnO₄ in acetone³ and 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid (IV) m.p. 262°-63° (decomp.) was obtained. This acid has also been prepared by Silberg⁴ who reported the same melting point for this acid. On decarboxylation of this acid with sodalime 7,8-benzoquinoline⁵ (V) m.p. 51°-52° was obtained, which gave silky picrate m.p. 190°-91°.

In 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid absorption at 3000 cm⁻¹ (broad) shows the presence of hydrogen bonded acid -O-H...O<. A very strong band at 1685 cm⁻¹ is due to C = O of the carboxylic acid. The absence of these bands in compounds (I), (II) and (III) shows the absence of carbonyl group in them.

This dicarboxylic acid is claimed to have been prepared by Schenck and Bailey⁶ by oxidation of base (I) with SeO₂ and they reported its m.p. to be 162°-63°. We also carried out oxidation of base (I) with SeO₂ and obtained an acid which melted at 260°-61°. There was no depression in melting point, when m.p. of this acid was taken in admixture with the acid (IV). Therefore m.p. 162°-63° reported by Schenck and Bailey for this acid does not seem to be correct. We have already reported the m.p. of 4-methyl-7,8-benzoquinoline-2-carboxylic acid to be 186° and it is expected that m.p. of 7,8-benzoquinoline-2,4-dicarboxylic acid should be higher than that of mono carboxylic acid. Hence m.p. 262°-63° for dicarboxylic acid (IV) is reasonably correct.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected and IR spectra were taken in KBr.

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline (I)

2,4-Dimethyl-7,8-benzoquinoline was prepared by following the method of Combes². Recrystallised from ethanol colourless crystals, m.p. 54°-55°. (Found : C, 86.5; H, 6.4. C₁₅H₁₃N requires C, 86.9; H, 6.2%) ν_{max} 1451 (CH₃), 754 (four adjacent H), 802 and 863 (two adjacent H) and 887 cm⁻¹ (one isolated H).